

Does generation matter? A comparison between travel behaviour and factors affecting on travel decision of generation Y and Z

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Abstract:

This study aimed to examine the differences in travel behaviours and attitudes toward factors affecting travel decisions between Generation (Gen) Y and generation Z Thai tourists. Moreover, this study proposes a tourism marketing strategy to promote tourism for both generations. The samples size of this study was 400 Gen Y and generation Z Thai tourists. The online questionnaire was used to collect data through Facebook fan pages. The result yielded that Gen Y and Gen Z Thai tourists shared many similar travel behaviours, such as travel objectives, transportation, the season of traveling, favourite areas, days of travel, frequency, and sources of information. The author recommended that cultural tourism, eco-tourism, and adventure tourism would fit the needs of these cohorts. Influencer marketing should be implemented to encourage sales promotion toward these generations. Moreover, the popular type of social media should be used to fit with the character of each generation.

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1. Introduction

The tourism industry has been accepted for its significance as a vital source of revenue for many countries. In 2019, the tourism industry worldwide grew 4% from the year 2018 and reached 1.5 billion US\$ in marketing value. Therefore, 2019 was another year of strong growth, although growth was slower compared to the exceptional rates of 2017 (+6%) and 2018 (+6%) due to the economic situation (The United Nation Tourism Organisation, 2020). Thailand is one of the countries that have enjoyed the rise of the tourism industry in the past few years. According to the Thailand Intelligence Tourism Centre (2019), this industry generated 2.5 trillion baht in 2018. Further, BLT Bangkok (2020) reported that the rapid growth of Thai tourism in 2019 has made Thailand the 4th-ranked country globally that gained the highest revenue from the tourism industry. This was partly due to the government's tourism campaigns to promote internal tourism, either to international or domestic tourists. By the way, the year 2020 has not been a good year for the tourism industry in Thailand, partly due to several negative factors such as an economic recession in Europe and the United States, a trade war between China and the USA, and P.M. 2.5 air pollution. Therefore, the government has paid more attention to encouraging Thais to travel in their own country to retain the growth of the industry. Many promotional campaigns have been launched, for instance "Thai Teaw Thai" (Thai people travel in Thailand) Exhibition; "Teaw Won Thammada Raka Chock Lok" (Travel on a weekday at a super special price); "Roi Deaw Teaw Tou Thai" (Travel over Thailand at only one hundred baht) (Tourism Authority of Thailand, 2019). However, these efforts have to be sustained due to the outbreak of the pandemic "Coronavirus" (Covid19), which threatens health and lives, as well as the global economy. The tourism industry is one of the industries that receive a huge impact from this pandemic. Most countries decided to go on lockdown to try to stop the transmission of this disease (Bangkokinsight, 2020). Some Thai experts evaluated that, if the outbreak continues until July, Thailand will lose 12.8 million tourists compared to those in 2019. If this outbreak cannot be contained by the end of 2020, however, the country will lose about 30 million international tourists compared to those of last year (Bangkokbiznews, 2020). Even though this outbreak is over, the international tourists will not travel soon due to their fear of disease and the economic recession. To revive the tourism situation in Thailand, the government should firstly focus on encouraging domestic tourists to travel in the country. A marketing strategy is a vital tool that enables marketers to achieve their goals.

So far, the concept of demographic generations has been accepted and applied to the development of the marketing strategy. This concept conveys that a collection of people who were born over a period of roughly twenty years and has witnessed similar key historical events is likely to share common beliefs, attitudes, and values, which lead to distinctive characteristics and behaviours. Therefore, in developing a marketing strategy for each generation, marketers should understand the differences in travel behaviours as well as the factors that affect their travel decisions (Marketing factors). Currently, people are classified into generations by their year of birth and the significant events they have shared, such as the Baby Boomers, who were born after the end of World War II. Generation X was born during the rise of the economy when the divorce rate was rising and birth control was generally accepted among the people. Generation Y was born at the beginning of the Millennium, and Generation Z include those who were born in the digital era, where social networking is very popular (Strauss & Howe, 1997). However, I emphasise my study on Generation Y and Generation Z according to Thansethakij (2017), who altogether represent 44.17% of the 67 million people in the Thai population. This makes them the potential population for domestic tourism for now and for the future. This study aims to enhance the understanding of the differences in travel behaviours and factors affecting travel decision between Generation Y

and Generation Z Thai tourists. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to government agencies concerned with the tourism industry in Thailand and other countries in Asia in developing tourism strategies that can effectively respond to the needs of the different young generations in society. This study seeks to identify the differences in travel behaviours and the attitudes toward factors affecting travel decisions between Generation Y and Generation Z Thai tourists. Moreover, it aims to propose a tourism marketing strategy for Generation Y and Generation Z Thai tourists.

2. Theoretical foundation and hypotheses development

2.1. The generation theory

A generation refers to a collection of people who were born over a period of roughly twenty years, or about a length of one's cycle of life. This includes childhood, young adulthood, midlife, and old age. Typically, we identify the particular generations from the first birth year to last (Pilcher, 1994). The people in one generation generally share three criteria, as follows (Lifecourse Associated, 2020). First, key historical events and social trends, such as World War II, the Internet, iPhone & iPad, Hamburger Crisis, Facebook, and Disruptiveness. Second, common beliefs and behaviours, including basic attitudes, culture, values, civic engagement, and family life. Third, perceived membership, meaning the people of the same generation tend to have a sense of commonality in recognising members of that generation and be able to identify themselves as an unique group with a different outlook from those outside their generation. In 1952, the social scientist "Karl Mannheim" conceptualised the generation concept and proposed a theory on the topic in his seminal essay, "*The Problem of Generations*". Mannheim accentuated the significance of generations as the reason behind the structure of social and intellectual movements. More recently, William Strauss and Neil Howe proposed a Generation theory also known as the "Fourth Turning" theory in their 1991 book "Generation", which analysed the history of the United States using a series of generational biographies. Later, they expanded their theory to focus on a four-fold cycle of generational types and recurring mood eras in their 1997 book "*The Fourth Turning*". These four cycles, so called the fourth turnings, include "The High", "The Awakening", "The Unravelling", and "The Crisis".

Though their theory intended to describe the history of the United States, they also examined the generational trends in other developed countries and described similar cycles (Strauss & Howe, 2009). Since then, the generation concept has been used widely in social sciences, mostly in management, human resources, information system, and marketing (e.g. Cho & Hu, 2009; Fukuda, 2010; Schewe & Meredith, 2004). In tourism and hospitality, the study of the travel behaviour of particular generations is the first step to help entrepreneurs and the government in developing a tourism marketing strategy that is able to respond to the needs of the tourists of different generations in society (Rudolph & Zecher, 2018).

2.2. Classification of generations

Recently, the global population has been classified into generations by the year of birth and the significant events they have shared, such as the Baby Boomers, which comprise a cohort of people who were born after the end of World War II. Generation X was born during the prosperous economy, where the divorce rate was rising and birth control was generally accepted among the people. Generation Y (Gen Y) people were born from the beginning of the Millennium onward. Millennials are sometimes called the "echo boomers" owing to the rise of birth rates since this generation is often the children of the Baby Boomers. Further, this generation is generally marked by their age of birth, which was the Information Age.

Meanwhile, those in Generation Z were born in the digital era and era of social networking (Bialik & Fry, 2019).

There is no common view among academics on the year of birth for each generation. For instance, Smith & Nichols (2018) stated that the Baby Boomer generation is anyone born between 1943 and 1960, while those in Generation X were born between 1961 and 1979. Generation Y refers to the people who were born between 1980 and 2000, while those in Generation Z were born from 2001 onward. The U.S. Chamber of Commerce Foundation (2012) defined the Baby Boomer generation as anyone who was born between 1946 and 1964, while Generation X was born between 1965 and 1979. Generation Y are the people who were born from between 1980-2000, while Generation Z was born from 2001 and onward. Bialik & Fry (2019) revealed the years that were used to classify demographic generations: the Baby Boomer generation was born between 1946 and 1964. Generation X people were born between 1965 and 1980, while Generation Y was the people who were born between 1981 and 2000. Generation Z people were born from 2001 onward. This study focuses on the tourists that belong to Generation Y, and according to many scholars were the people born between 1980-1994 (26- 40 years old) (Tapscott, 2010; Levickaite,2010; Singh, 2014; Baltescu, 2019; Tanaid & Wright,2019) and Generation Z who were born between 1995-2010 (10-25 years old) as suggested by Weiler (2005), Chicioreanu & AMZA(2018), Cavagnaro, Staffieri & Postma (2018), Panwar & Mehta (2019). These two generations together added up to 44% of the global population. Therefore, the tourism industry depends on them (Security and Exchange Commission, 2019).

2.3. Travel behaviour of the tourists

The topic of travel behaviour has gained more and more attention from researchers and academicians these days. The specific theory of travel behaviour was developed in addition to general theories from the fields of economics, geography, and psychology. It was theorised firstly to explain the relationships and factors influencing transportation choices. For instance, the “*Attitude Theory*” was proposed by Fishbein & Ajzen (1975) concerning travel behaviour perspective. They stated that, unless forced by social, monetary, or physical means, a change in travel behaviour is determined by a change in beliefs, attitudes, and/or values (Fujii & Gärling, 2003).

Later, Golob (2001) added that a forced change of travel behaviour could cause a change in beliefs, attitudes, and/or values. However, Fujii & Gärling (2006) urged that this change was likely to be true if the outcome was positive. In other cases, a forced change has been shown to result in increased resistance (Brehm & Brehm, 1981). For example, a monetary payoff was one of the forced factors that influenced the travel behavioural change. However, this change was frequently only temporary and did not remain after the monetary payoff was discontinued. Thus, it is implied that some internal changes in cognitive skills, beliefs, attitudes, or values are the vital determinants of a permanent behavioural change. Axhausen & Gärling (1992) added that travel choice was presumed to be dependent upon biological needs, obligations, or desires to engage in various activities at different places.

The “*Choice Theories*” explained that travel choices such as choices of destination, departure time, vehicle, and route can be varied depend on the determinants, such as higher cost, time saving, etc. (Hensher, 1994; Keeney & Raiffa, 1993; McFadden, 2001).

The “*Habit-Formation*” Theory explained how the people’s habits influence their travel behaviour. Ronis, Yates, & Kirscht (1989) defined a habit as a repeated choice. Bargh (1997)

suggested that the habits could be strengthened by positive feedback, while they might be weakened by negative hedonic feedback. Verplanken Aarts & Van Knippenberg (1997) added that the habits were assumed to depend on storage in the long-term memory of scripts (Abelson, 1981) or ready-made choice rules that can be retrieved. Thus, choices require minimal search for external information (Gärling, 2004). Based on habit-formation theories, it can be reckoned that changes in travel behaviour are not likely to occur unless changes in travel options are very dominant and yield positive outcomes (Fujii & Gärling, 2005; Garvill, Marell, & Nordlund, 2003).

Fujii & Garling (2005) proposed that there are two methods concerning the change in behaviour. The first method is called “the structural method”, which focuses on changing behaviour by economic and physical factors. The other is “the psychological method” emphasising the psychological factors such as attitude, belief, value, etc. From the aforementioned theories, we can conclude that the tourists’ behaviour may vary depending upon different types of determinants such as psychological factors including attitude, belief, value, personality, etc. As Fujii & Gärling (2006) stated, the members of a generation tend to share some common beliefs and behaviours, including basic attitudes, culture, values, civic engagement, and family life. Therefore, we can conclude that the people of different generations tend to have different travel behaviours.

2.4. Travel behaviour of generation Y and Z

The issue of “Generational difference” in terms of travel behaviour has obtained the interests of many researchers and academicians, so far, not to mentioned the within -generational differences. In this study, I focus on the differences in the travel behaviour of Generation Y and Generation Z Thai tourists. Since these two generations are the potential target group for tourism in Thai tourism in the future. According to Yoon & Uysal (2005) the two generations have to share some common characteristics. They are marked as the creators and early adopters of new trends since both generations are familiar with new technologies. However, there are some differences between them. Generation Y members were born between 1980 and the early part of the new millennium (Postolov, Sopova, & Iliev, 2017). That is how they got the name “Millennials”. This generation is represented by the internet and increasing connections to the world. Being protected by their parents, they grew up with the belief that anything is possible. They are also characterised as optimistic, social, open to changes, and have high expectations of themselves and others (PrincetonOne, 2017).

Generation Z or the Post-millennials were born at the beginning of the new millennium (Postolov, Sopova & Iliev 2017). They are known as Gen Z or I Generation. These groups of people are familiar with high sophisticated media and the computer environment as a normal state. The Post-millennials, on the contrary, tend to be more individualistic, less focused, better multi-taskers, entrepreneurial, and more globally oriented with higher expectations (Beall, 2017). According to a Bloomberg analysis of United Nations data, Gen Z purchasing power was estimated at \$29 billion to \$143 billion in direct spending. They also have significant influence on family and household purchases. According to WYSE Travel Confederation (2018), tourist ‘characteristics have influences on the young generation’s travel habits. As the study showed, there was a shift towards placing the value on experiences rather than material things. Further, a survey result conducted by Tripadvisor (2016) revealed that 57% of Americans constantly save money specifically for traveling, while 68% of the Millennials do the same. Moreover, it was found that the tourists under 30 years old are most likely to spend their money on food and drink experiences (37%), events and festivals (27%), fine and performing arts (18%). Meanwhile, using guidebooks in travelling is popular

among those older than 65 years (36% use guidebooks while traveling), and the least popular with 18-24s. On the other hand, face-to-face and digital word of mouth have a significant influence on younger travellers.

Generation Y and Z were found to prefer travelling to less-visited destinations, a different world region and stay for a longer period. Moreover, the more activities and experiences they gained from the destination, the happier with their travel they were. Regarding accommodation booking, it was found that the Post-millennials were more likely to make online bookings than the Millennials. Additionally, travellers of Generation Z are more socialise than Generation Y (WYSE Travel Confederation, 2018). The study conducted by Expedia and the Centre for Generational Kinetics (2018) on the population of the USA revealed the differences in behaviour between Generation Y and Generation Z regarding travel companion that 58% of Generation Z's respondents travel with parents, while only 24% of Generation Y respondents travel with their parents. Compared to the other generations, more than one-third of Americans have travelled alone for leisure in the past years. Another study conducted by Carson Wagonlit Travel (2017) focused on the travel behaviour of business people from different countries. The findings showed that almost 60 % of the Millennial business people travelled with others, 43% travelled with colleagues and 15% with friends and family. This makes millennials least likely to travel alone when going on a business trip (Resonance Consultancy, 2018). When compares to previous generations, the Millennials are, in general, far more flexible on alternative of accommodations (Gelfeld, 2017). They are more influenced by special offers, proximity to transport options and sustainable travel than previous generations (Resonance Consultancy report, 2018). Regarding transportation options, low cost airlines are the prime choice of millennials (Fromm, 2018).

According to a global study conducted by Booking.com in 2018 (2019), one of the largest travel e-commercials companies in the world, 60% of all travellers intend to post their travel experience on social media each day, where the younger generation are more likely to see it. 84% of millennials post their vacations on social media. They share their experiences using Facebook, Instagram and Tripadvisor (2016) platforms. While almost similar per cent, 80% of the Generation Z tourists intended to post their travel experiences to Facebook, Instagram, etc. Sutthiwetin & Buasorn (2019) conducted a study on "Tourism Marketing Promotion Strategy which Influence Tourism Motivation to Generation Z in Bangkok Metropolitan Region" and found that marketing strategy influences the motivation to travel for Generation Z. Meanwhile, the marketing promotion which attracted Generation Z tourists was advertising through social media, public relations through social media, newspaper, magazine, online personnel selling, and price reduction. From the literature concerning travel behaviours, it was found that though these two generations have something in common, there were some differences in their travel behaviour. For instance, Generation Z tourists travel with their parents and make hotel bookings via online channels more than Generation Y. In order to clarify the differences in travel behaviour for the two generations, this study intends to further explore the travel behaviours of Generation Y and Generation Z tourists, such as the reasons for travelling, destination of travel, transportation, accommodation, types of tourism preference, budget for travelling, etc. This knowledge will be useful for the tourism business in formulating a marketing strategy to promote domestic tourism in the country.

2.5. Factors affecting the travel decisions of tourists

The understanding of tourist behaviour and travel motivation is important for tourism entrepreneurs who want to create demand and help tourists in decision-making (Blackwell, Miniard, & Engel, 2005). According to Mammadov (2013), "consumer behaviour" can be

described as consumer attitude, decisions, activities, ideas or experiences in using, purchasing, evaluating and searching of products and services that satisfy needs (Hsu, Tsai & Wu, 2009).

Consumer behaviour includes the process that formulates decisions to spend accessible assets (time, money, effort) on buying things. Friman, Garling, Ettema, & Olsson (2017) stated that tourist behaviour is the direct result of continuous interaction between certain personal and environmental variables. Whereby, decision-making is the procedure of recognising and choosing from among available solutions of a problem according to the demands of the circumstance (Pierret, 2011). According to Schiffman, O'Cass, Paladino, & Carlson (2014), the process of tourist decision-making regarding the destination selection is influenced by different changeable factors. The internal factors included desire for escape, rest, relaxation, prestige, health and fitness, adventure, and social interaction, etc. While, the external factors are based on attractiveness of the destination, including tangible resources, and tourist's perceptions and expectations (Smallman & Moore, 2010). According to Kottler & Keller (2006) consumer purchase decision is influenced by the External factor which comprises the economic factor and the marketing factor. The internal factor contends the psychological factor and consumers' characteristics. While, the internal factors and the economic factors are difficult to control, the marketing factors (price, place, product, promotion) are the ones that can be formulated and managed by the marketers.

Prior researches have also shown the influence of the marketing factors on the travel decisions of tourists. For instance, Arwatchanakarn (2015) conducted a study concerning the influence of the marketing factor on the behaviour of sustainable cultural tourists in a province in Thailand and found that the marketing factor has an influence on the behaviour of sustainable cultural tourists. Noppakhun (2019) studied the effects of tourism marketing factors on the foreign divers' decision to go scuba diving in Thailand and found that the tourism marketing factor had a positive correlation to the foreign divers' decision in Thailand. Moreover, a study on the influential factors of the marketing of Buddhism Tourism in Chaiyaphum Province by Chaisri, Srida & Tupod, (2019) revealed that the influential factors of marketing have an influence on the decision to travel by Buddhism Tourism travellers. Moreover, the related researches had found the differences in the attitude toward the tourism marketing mix among the tourists with different ages as follows;

Merritt, Kline, Crawford, Viren, & Dilworth (2018) examine the potential differences in preferred vacation activities among three generational cohorts using psychographic analysis. This study found specific differences across generations, with Generation Y preferred more active activities than other groups such as beach activities, walking, kayaking, and biking. From this study, I infer that there are differences in the tourists' attitudes toward tourism products among tourists with different generations. Moreover, Likitsarun et al. (2019) studied the tourists' opinion with different demographic characteristics toward the marketing mix for the tourism Management in Phichit Province, Thailand. It was found that tourists of different ages had different opinions toward product, place, promotion, physical evidence, people, and process. From these studies, I infer that the tourists of different ages (generations) have a different attitude toward the marketing mix regarding the "Product". Therefore, I set the first hypothesis that;

H1: There is a significant difference in the attitude of Generation Y and Generation Z Thai tourists toward "Product".

Deeprasert (2016) explored the effect of ages on the marketing mix factors in historical, art, cultural, and traditional tourism of Nakhon Phanom province. The finding revealed that tourists of different ages placed different importance levels on the marketing mix. The tourists at the age of between 49 and 58 paid higher attention to promotion than those whose ages were in the 39-48 age range on the marketing mix factors. In addition, the tourists whose ages were between 39-48 years old placed higher importance on the price that those whose age was in the 19-28 age range. The tourists at the age of 19-28 years old gave higher significance to types of tourism. Likitsarun et al. (2019) studied the tourists’ opinion with different demographic characteristics toward the marketing mix for the tourism Management in Phichit Province, Thailand. It was found that tourists of different ages had different opinions toward product, place, promotion, physical evidence, people, and process. From these related researches, I infer that the tourists of different ages (generations) have a different attitude toward the marketing mix concerning price place promotion. Therefore, the second-fourth hypothesis was set that:

H2: There is a significant difference in the attitude of Generation Y and Generation Z Thai tourists toward “Price”.

H3: There is a significant difference in the attitude of Generation Y and Generation Z Thai tourists toward “Place”. (Channel of distribution)

H4: There is a significant difference in the attitude of Generation Y and Generation Z Thai tourists toward “Promotion”.

The concept of this study can be conceptualised based upon the review of literature and research hypotheses as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

3. Methods

In order to find solutions for this study, the author conducted research according to the following procedures.

3.1. Research methodology

A quantitative research was employed to this study, which is consistent with what Apuke (2017) suggested that a quantitative research methodology is appropriate for a study that requires collection from a large sample size.

3.2. Population and samples

The population of this study comprised Thai people whose ages can be categorised as Generation Y (26- 40 years old) and Generation Z (15- 25 years old). The number of Generation Y in Thailand is around 19,000,000, while the number of Generation Z is around 10,600,000 (Thansettakij, 2020). The sample size of this study was derived from Yamane's sample size formula; $n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$. Where n = corrected sample size, N = population size and e = margin of error = 0.05 (Yamane, 1973) *Statistics: An Introductory Analysis*. 3rd Ed. The results of the calculation yielded the sample size of 389. However, 400 units of the samples were applied to this study to be able to evenly divide the samples into two groups (Gen Y & Gen Z).

3.3. Research instruments

3.3.1. Development of research instrument

A self-administered questionnaire was used as a data collection tool in this study. The scales comprised in the questionnaire were developed based upon the review of prior researches to respond to the research objectives. The structure was divided into 3 parts as detailed below:

Part I: Personal Information about the respondents, comprising the closed-end questions concerning the respondents' personal information, such as gender, age, education, etc.

Part II: Travel Behaviour comprises the closed-end questions concerning the respondents' domestic travel behaviour, such as objectives of travelling, frequency of travelling, etc.

Part III: Factors affecting the respondents decision on domestic travel, comprised the five-levels rating scales questions concerning the respondent's attitude toward marketing factors affecting the respondents decision on domestic travelling, such as product, price, place, and promotion.

3.4. Test of the research instrument

The questionnaire was tested for reliability by conducting a pilot test on 30 Thai people whose ages were between 15-40 (GenY and Gen Z). The collected data was analysed to obtain the Cronbach's Alpha statistics. The result yields the Cronbach's Alpha of overall questionnaire at 0.875, which is considered reliable (Taber, 2018).

3.5. Data collection

The data collection was conducted through online channels. The questionnaire was developed using the Google Docs application. I posted the link of the online questionnaire onto Facebook pages concerning tourism and hospitality, asking the pages' members to answer the questionnaires. After the number of samples reached 400, I downloaded the gathered data from Google Docs application.

4. Data Analysis

The data was compiled and analysed via a statistical analysis program, using 2 types of the statistics, which were 1) descriptive statistics, such as frequency and percentage, to describe the respondents' personal characteristics. The cross-tabulation technique was used in comparing travel behaviour between GenY and Gen Z. 2) The inferential statistics, which was the independent t-test, was employed in testing the differences between the attitude toward factors affecting travel decisions of Gen Y and Gen Z, according to the research hypothesis.

4.1. Results

In this part, the results of the research analysis are presented based upon the objectives of the research, which are:

4.1.1. Domestic travel behaviours of generation Y and Z

4.1.1.1. Travel objective

The analysis results reveal that most of Generation Y and Generation Z share similar travel objectives, which are to relax the body and mind (Gen Y=91.0% Gen Z 88.5%) However, Gen Y placed their second and third priorities on energizing their lives (66.5%) and on tasting the local food from different areas (55.5%). Most of Generation Z, however, placed their second and third priorities on learning different cultures (73.5%) and learning about people and places (64.5%), as presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Travel objectives

Generation	relax body and mind	power up life	Seeking for excitement and adventure	learn about people and places	learn different Culture	taste local food from different areas	seeking for relationships	Others
Y	182 91.0%	131 65.5%	69 34.5%	108 54.0%	103 51.5%	111 55.5%	26 13.0%	9 4.5%
Z	177 88.5%	122 61.0%	118 59.0%	129 64.5%	147 73.5%	112 56.0%	67 33.5%	8 4.0%

Source: Results from the IBM SPSS 25.0 output

4.1.1.2. Travel frequency

Regarding travel frequency, Generation Y and Generation Z shared similar travel frequency in the way that the majority of both generations travelled 1-more than 1 time/ month (Gen Y=36.5; Gen Z = 35.0%). However, we found 19.5% of Gen Y travelled 1 time/year, followed by 1 time/ 2-3 months (12.0%), respectively. Around 26.5 % of Gen Z travelled 1 time per 2-3 months and 20% of them travelled 1 time/year.

Table 2 Travel frequency

Generation	Frequency				Total
	One -more than one time per month	1 time/2-3 months	1 time/year	Not sure	
Y	73 36.5 %	24 12.0%	39 19.5%	64 32.0%	200 100.0%
Z	70 35.0%	53 26.5%	40 20.0%	37 18.5%	200 100.0%
Total	77 19.3%	104 65.0%	134 33.5%	79 19.8%	110 27.5%

Source: Results from the IBM SPSS 25.0 output

4.1.1.3. *Transportation*

The analysis results revealed that, similar to Generation Z, the majority of Generation Y respondents travelled by personal car (Gen Y= 56.5%, Gen Z=57%), followed by plane (Gen Y =26.0%, Gen Z = 23.0%) and bus (Gen Y =6.5%, Gen Z=13.5%), as shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Travel transportation

Generation	Transportation							Total
	Personal Car	Bus	Train	SkyTrain	Tourist Bus	Plane	Other	
Y	113	13	0	4	5	52	13	200
	56.5%	6.5%	0.0%	2.0%	2.5%	26.0%	6.5%	100.0%
Z	114	27	13	0	0	46	0	200
	57.0%	13.5%	6.5%	0.0%	0.0%	23.0%	0.0%	100.0%
Total	227	40	13	4	5	98	13	400
	56.8%	10.0%	3.3%	1.0%	1.3%	24.5%	3.3%	100.0%

Source: Results from the IBM SPSS 25.0 output

4.1.1.4. *Days of Travelling*

The findings revealed that, similar to Generation Z, Generation Y respondents travelled mostly on the weekend (Gen Y = 45.5%, Gen Z=37.5%) followed by holidays (GenY= 29.0%, Gen Z =33.5%), and weekdays (Gen Y =19.5%, Gen Z=25.0%).

Table 4 Days of travel

Generation	Time				Total
	Weekend	Holiday	Weekday	Uncertain	
Y	91	58	39	12	200
	45.5%	29.0%	19.5%	6.0%	100.0%
Z	75	67	50	8	200
	37.5%	33.5%	25.0%	4.0%	100.0%
Total	166	125	89	20	400
	41.5%	31.3%	22.3%	5.0%	100.0%

Source: Results from the IBM SPSS 25.0 output

4.1.1.5. *Season of travel*

The findings pointed out that both Generation Y and Generation Z shared a similar pattern regarding the seasons of travel. However, these two generations travelled mostly during the summer (Gen y=62.0%, Gen Z 63.0%), followed by winter (Gen Y =26.5%, Gen Z = 20.5%) and rainy season (Gen y=4.5%, Gen Z 8.5%).

Table 5 Season of travel

Generation	Season				Total
	Winter	Rainy season	Summer	Uncertain	
Y	53	9	124	14	200
	26.5%	4.5%	62.0%	7.0%	100.0%
Z	41	17	126	16	200
	20.5%	8.5%	63.0%	8.0%	100.0%
Total	94	26	250	30	400
	23.5%	6.5%	62.5%	7.5%	100.0%

Source: Results from the IBM SPSS 25.0 output

4.1.1.6. *Sources of information*

From the analysis results, both Generation Y and Generation Z shared similar sources of information concerning the first and second places. However, the majority of them looked for traveling information from the online social networks (Gen Y = 90.5%, Gen Z =89.5%),

followed by word of mouth from friends and other people. (Gen Y =37.5%, Gen Z=55.5%). However, we found, regarding the third place, Gen Y looked for tourism information from tourism magazines (22.0%), while Gen Z sought tourism information from exhibitions (32.0%).

Table 6 Sources of information (Answer more than one)

Generation	Sources of information									
	Tourism Magazine	Online Social Network	Tourism Websites	Radio	Television	Newspaper	Word of mouth	Brochures / leaflets	Exhibition	Others
Y	44 22.0%	181 90.5%	42 21.0%	5 2.5%	28 14.0%	9 4.5%	75 37.5%	22 11.0%	34 17.0%	0 0.0%
Z	38 19.0%	179 89.5%	44 22.0%	5 2.5%	51 25.5%	19 9.5%	111 55.5%	24 12.0%	64 32.0%	8 4.0%

Source: Results from the IBM SPSS 25.0 output

4.1.1.7. Types of travelling

The findings showed that both Generation Y and Generation Z travelled mostly by themselves (Gen Y = 89.0%, Gen Z = 82.5%). Only a few travelled with a package tour (Gen Y = 11.0%, Gen Z = 17.5%), as presented in Table 7.

Table 7 Types of travel

Generation	Format		Total
	Package Tour	Personal	
Y	22 11.0%	178 89.0%	200 100.0%
Z	35 17.5%	165 82.5%	200 100.0%
Total	57 14.3%	343 85.8%	400 100.0%

Source: Results from the IBM SPSS 25.0 output

4.1.1.8. Travel companies

The findings reveal the differences with respect to travel companies between the two generations. The majority of Gen Y travelled mostly with their partners (36.0%), followed by family (32.0%) and friends (19.5%), while the majority of Generation Z travelled with family (42.5%), followed by friends (34.5%) and lovers (20.5%), as shown in Table 8.

Table 8 Travel companies

Generation	Who with				Total
	Self	Lover	Family	Friends	
Y	25 12.5%	72 36.0%	64 32.0%	39 19.5%	200 100.0%
Z	5 2.5%	41 20.5%	85 42.5%	69 34.5%	200 100.0%
Total	30 7.5%	113 28.3%	149 37.3%	108 27.0%	400 100.0%

Source: Results from the IBM SPSS 25.0 output

4.1.1.9. Travel decisions

The findings revealed the differences regarding travel decisions between the two generations. With respect to Gen Y, the people who had the most influence on their travel decisions were their lovers (34.5%), followed by themselves (25.5%) and family (20.5%). As for Generation Z, the persons who had influence on their travel decisions were their family (49.5%), followed by lovers (20.5%) and friends (15.5%).

Table 9 Travel decisions

Generation	Decision				Total
	Self	Lover	Family	Friends	
Y	51	69	41	39	200
	25.5%	34.5%	20.5%	19.5%	100.0%
Z	29	41	99	31	200
	14.5%	20.5%	49.5%	15.5%	100.0%
Total	80	110	140	70	400
	20.0%	27.5%	35.0%	17.5%	100.0%

Source: Results from the IBM SPSS 25.0 output

4.1.1.10. Travel budget

From the analysis of results, I found differences with respect to the travel budget between these two generations. The majority of Gen Y set their travel budget higher than 10,000 baht (31.0%), followed by 1,001-3,000 baht (27.0%) and 3,001-5,000 baht (21.0%). Meanwhile, the majority of Gen Z set their travel budget to between 1,001-3000 baht (36.5%), followed by 3,001-5,000 baht (28.0%) and more than 10,000 baht (17.5%).

Table 10 Budget for Travel

Generation	Budget							Total
	Lower Baht	1,000 Baht	1,001-3,000 Baht	3,001-5,000 Baht	5,001-7,000 Baht	7,001- 10,000 Baht	More than 10,000 Baht	
Y	0	54	42	17	25	62	200	
	0.0%	27.0%	21.0%	8.5%	12.5%	31.0%	100.0%	
Z	8	73	56	28	0	35	200	
	4.0%	36.5%	28.0%	14.0%	0.0%	17.5%	100.0%	
Total	8	127	98	45	25	97	400	
	2.0%	31.8%	24.5%	11.3%	6.3%	24.3%	100.0%	

Source: Results from the IBM SPSS 25.0 output

4.1.1.11. Interested types of tourism

The analysis of results showed differences between Generation Y and Generation Z's interest in terms of types of tourism. By which, the majority of Generation Y were interested in eco-tourism, while most of Generation Z were interested in cultural tourism. Moreover, the majority of Generation Y was interested in cultural tourism as the second place and historical tourism as the third place. Most of Generation Z was interested in eco-tourism as the second place and recreation/entertainment as the third place, as shown in Table 11.

Table 11 Interested types of tourism (Can answer more than one)

Generation	Interest					
	Eco Tourism	Historical Tourism	Cultural Tourism	Shopping	Recreation/ Entertainment	Others
Y	125	85	98	80	79	4
	62.5%	42.5%	49.0%	40.0%	39.5%	2.0%
Z	108	80	97	84	149	12
	54.5%	40.4%	75.3%	42.4%	49.0%	6.1%

Source: Results from the IBM SPSS 25.0 output

4.1.1.12. Tourists destinations

The outcome reveals a similarity in tourist destination between Generation Y and Generation Z. The majority of Gen Y and Gen Z indicated their tourist destination as the northern part of Thailand (Gen Y =39.5% Gen Z =), followed by the eastern part (Gen Y =16.0% Gen Z =20.5) and southern part (Gen Y =15.0 Gen Z=14.5%), as presented in Table 12

Table 12 Tourist destinations

Generation	Region						Total
	Bangkok	Northern	Central	East	East-West	Southern	
Z	8 4.0%	79 39.5%	24 12.0%	41 20.5%	19 9.5%	29 14.5%	200 100.0%
Y	30 15.0%	91 45.5%	9 4.5%	32 16.0%	8 4.0%	30 15.0%	200 100.0%

Source: Results from the IBM SPSS 25.0 output

4.1.1.13. Tourist attitude towards the significance of marketing mix on their travel decision

The findings indicated a similarity in the attitude toward marketing mix between the two generations. The majority of Generation Y and Generation Z put the product as the number one priority. However, Gen Y placed the price in second place, followed by promotion and place, while Gen Z put promotion in the second place, followed by price and place, as detailed in Table 13.

Table 13 Tourist attitude towards the marketing mix

Description	Gen Z		Gen Y		level
	M	SD	M	SD	
	Product (Tourist destination)	3.95	0.763	4.10	
Price	3.60	0.727	3.89	0.453	Agree
Place	3.57	0.824	3.71	0.900	Agree
Promotion	3.67	1.005	3.85	0.760	Agree

Source: Results from the IBM SPSS 25.0 output

4.2. Hypothesis test

The t-test statistic was used to test the research hypotheses of the study, as presented in Table 14.

Table 14 Differences in Attitude towards Marketing Factors Affecting Travel Decisions between Generation Y and Generation Z

Variables	Generation	\bar{X}	S.D.	t-value	df	p-value
Product	Z	3.95	0.763	1.800	398	.073
	Y	4.10	0.867			
Price	Z	3.60	0.727	*-4.836	398	.000
	Y	3.89	0.453			
Place	Z	3.57	0.824	-1.588	398	.113
	Y	3.71	0.900			
Promotion	Z	3.67	1.005	*2.065	398	.040
	Y	3.85	0.760			

P-value <.05

Source: Results from the IBM SPSS 25.0 output

From Table 14, the analysis results via t-test reveal no significant difference in the attitude towards Product and Place between Generation Z and Generation Y Thai tourists ($p > 0.05$).

However, differences are observed from the attitude toward Price and Promotion between the two generations ($p < 0.05$). Hence, the hypotheses test can be summarised as shown in Table 15.

Table 15 Results of Hypothesis Test

Hypothesis	P-value	Accept	Reject
H1: There is a significant difference in the attitude of Generation Y and Generation Z Thai tourists towards the Product (tourist's destination).	.073		/
H2: There is a significant difference in the attitude of Generation Y and Generation Z Thai tourists towards Price.	.000*	/	
H3: There is a significant difference in the attitude of Generation Y and Generation Z Thai tourists towards Place (channel of distribution)	.113		/
H4: There is a significant difference in the attitude of Generation Y and Generation Z Thai tourists towards Promotion.	.040*	/	

*P-value < 0.05

Source: Results from the IBM SPSS 25.0 output

5. Discussion and implications

In this section, the results of the study are discussed according to the objectives of the study, as follows:

1) The difference in travel behaviours between Generation Y and Generation Z Thai tourists. The findings of this study reveal that Thai tourists in Generation Y and Generation Z share many similar travel behaviours. For instance, they share a similar major travel objective, which is to relax their body and mind. Both generations preferred travelling by personal car, followed by plane. They also travelled mostly in the summer followed by the winter and on the weekend followed by a holiday. Their favourite area of travelling was the northern part of Thailand. Both generations share similar sources of information, which are websites and social networks.

These similarities are consistent with a survey conducted by the New Horizon Survey (WYSE Travel Confederation, 2018), which reported that “Gen Z travel behaviour is similar to that of Millennials; only they demonstrate a greater degree of these trends. For example, when we talk about the importance of social media for Millennials, it will play an even more significant role for Generation Z.” This conformity may be due to their closeness of birth years, which allows them to witness the resemblance of global context regarding economy, politics, social, and technology (Generation Y were born between 1980-1994 (26- 40 years old) followed closely by Generation Z who were born between 1995-2010 (10-25 years old)). According to Crappell (2015), many Millennials and Generation Z have been considered as “young adults”. This may be because both generations are highly connected to technology and the internet. With these similarities in mind, marketers reckon that it might be effective and cost-efficient to run only one campaign aimed at both generations. Additionally, Bump (2019) urged that there has been a common misconception that Generation Z and the Millennials are quite the same. Therefore, when the marketers discussed how to attract these young generations, they usually develop one marketing strategy which is believed to be fit to both groups.

If we look closely at the details of this research finding, however, we can observe some differences in travel behaviours between these two generations. For instance, if we look at their travel objectives, we can observe that, despite the similarity of their first travel objective, we have found that Gen Y placed their second and third priorities on energizing their lives and on tasting the local food from different areas. Meanwhile, most of Generation Z

placed their second and third priority on learning about different cultures and learning about people and places. These differences can be explained by a survey conducted by the New Horizon Survey (WYSE Travel Confederation, 2018), which suggested that, though both generations preferred experiential travel by which they can enjoy new experiences and emotions, by exploring the local flavours, cultural and natural experiences that will help them completely immerse into the destination. Generation Z is more social than the Millennials and values local connections more. That is, local experiences and meeting new people plays a more important role as their travel motivation.

The findings also revealed the differences with respect to travel companies between the two generations. The majority of Generation Y travelled mostly with their lovers, followed by family and friends, while the majority of Generation Z travelled with family, followed by friends and lovers. Another difference we found concerned their travel-decision influencers. With respect to Gen Y, the people who had the most influence on their travel decision were their lovers, followed by themselves and family. As for Generation Z, the people who had influence on their travel decisions were their family, followed by lovers and friends (15.5%). These results may be due to differences in stages of life between the two generations who were born at different periods of time; Generation Y was born between 1980-1994 (26- 40 years old), (Baltescu, 2019; Tanaid & Wright, 2019) while Generation Z refers to the young people who were born between 1995-2010 (10-25 years old) (Chicioeanu & AMZA, 2018).

According to their ages as mentioned, Generation Y people can be the managers in any organisation at present, while, Generation Y might have just entered into college or still be in school. Attaching to and depending on their parents and family support, Generation Z's travel decision may sometimes depend on their parents and family. They may also travel with their family more than Generation Y, despite their financial dependence, according to a Bloomberg analysis of United Nations data. Generation Z buying power is estimated at \$29 billion to \$143 billion in direct spending, and they also have a significant influence on family and household purchases (Miller & Lu, 2018). As for Thailand, a survey done by the Stock Exchange of Thailand in 2016 revealed that from approximately 66 million people in the country, 27% were Generation X, 28.54% were Generation Y and about 22% were Generation Z. Thus, there is no doubt that these two generations will become valuable target customers for the tourism industries in the near future (Security and Exchange Commission, 2020).

Another different issue we found concerned the types of tourism they were interested in. Whereby, the majority of Generation Y was interested in Eco-Tourism and most of Generation Z was interested in Cultural-Tourism. These differences can be explained by the study of The New Horizon Survey (WYSE Travel Confederation, 2018), which advised that both Millennials and Generation Z see travel as a way to enjoy new experiences and emotions, making travel one of the centres of the experience economy. Travellers look for local flavours, cultural and natural experiences that will help them immerse into the destination completely. Moreover, Gen Z is more social than Millennials; they want to learn about different cultures from the local people so that they can experience being a part of that culture while they are there.

2) The difference in the attitude toward factors affecting travel decision between Generation Y and Generation Z Thai tourists

The marketing factor is one of the factors that has an effect on travel decisions and behaviours of tourists. As a study conducted by Chantamart and Thabhiranrak (2018) revealed, the four marketing mix or 4Ps had an effect on the tourists' travel decision and behaviour at the floating market in terms of expenses spent at the market, and their

frequency of visiting the market, with the statistical significance of .05. A study organised by Noppakhun (2019) also showed that the marketing factors had a positive correlation on foreign divers' decision in Thailand at a significance level of 0.05.

According to this study, a similarity in the attitude toward marketing mix between the two generations was found. The majority of Generation Y and Generation Z gave the first priority to "Product". This implies that tourist destination has the most influence on the tourists, either General Y or Generation Z. According to a study conducted by the New Horizon Survey (WYSE Travel Confederation, 2018), the meaning of travelling has become similar to that of the word experiencing as both Millennials and Generation Z perceive travel as a way to enjoy new experiences and emotions. Young travellers these days often look for local flavours, cultural and natural experiences that will help them unite with the local people or the destination (WYSE Travel Confederation, 2018). However, a study conducted by the Expedia (2018) indicated that Generation Z craves travel experiences more than Generation Y. As they found, Gen Z was attracted to beach experiences, since 65% of them chose this type of destination, while only 54% of Millennials were attracted to beach destinations. Therefore, the similarity still shows some differences between the two generations. We found that both generations recognised the importance of money saving since Generation Y ranked "price" at the second place, while Generation Z put promotion at the second place. We also found that both generations ranked "place" or channel of distribution at the third place. However, Generation Z seemed to use smartphones in travelling more than Generation Y. According to WYSE Travel Confederation (2018), Generation Z was found to rely on smartphones more than Millennials since they are digital natives who were born and educated with the heavy use of technology.

3) Tourism marketing strategy for Generation Y and Generation Z Thai tourists. From literature reviews and the findings of this study, I suggest the marketing implications for Generation Y and Generation Z as follows:

5.1. Marketing implications

The findings of this study reveal that Thai tourists that belong to Generation Y and Generation Z share many similar travel behaviours, such as travel objectives, transportation, season of travelling, favourite areas, days of travel, frequency, and sources of information. A survey conducted by the New Horizon Survey (WYSE Travel Confederation, 2018) reported that "Gen Z travel behaviour is similar to that of Millennials, only they demonstrate a greater degree of these trends". However, there are still some differences in travel decisions and behaviour between the two generations. For instance, Generation Z placed their second and third priority on learning different cultures and learning about people and places, while Generation Y's motivation for travel was to relax and energize their lives from work. Generation Z was also found to use mobile phones for travelling more than Generation Y. Therefore, the market plan for each generation should be similar in some parts and different in some parts to fit each cohort.

5.2. Product (Tourist destination) implications

According to Deloitte Global Millennial survey, Millennial and Generation Z's travel trends are largely driven by their evolving aspirations, meaning "seeing and traveling the world" is their No. 1 aspiration. This implies that travel experience seems to be the thing they both expect most from travelling. Based upon the findings of this study, I suggest that the government should promote the tourism types that allow these younger generations to obtain travel experience, such as Cultural tourism, Eco-tourism, and Historical tourism, which are types of

tourism that allow them to learn new things apart from what they have learnt in the classroom. According to TripAdvisor (2016), Generations Y and Z are more likely to explore less-visited destinations. They prefer to travel to different regions and for longer periods. Therefore, the government and local tourism agencies should develop new tourist destinations and promote them to the two generations as the unseen.

According to the New Horizon Survey (WYSE Travel Confederation, 2018) for Generation Z, **self-improvement and self-awareness are becoming a more significant motivation to travel** compared to Millennials. It also seems that Gen Z is more social than Millennials and values local connections more. That is, local experiences and meeting new people play more important for Gen Z's travel decisions. Based on the review of literature and the findings of this study, Cultural tourism, Eco-tourism, and Adventure tourism seem to fit the needs of this cohort.

5.3. Price & promotion implications

Being born during an uncertain economy is a consequence of the Great Depression. Generation Y has been considered as materialistic and spoiled who set their dream goal to have their own house, car, and, setting up their family (Investopedia, 2020). To achieve their goal they seem to be money-saving conscious. However, the shift towards placing the value on experiences, rather than material things has been observed. According to TripAdvisor (2016), 68 % of the Millennials in America constantly save money specifically for traveling. They are willing to pay a higher price for better experiences. They are more focused on the worthiness of their money. Therefore, to set up prices that attract Generation Y's travellers, the marketers should be certain that they can deliver more value in terms of travel experiences, to this Generation. Moreover, I found from this study that both generations placed importance on the money they spent. Whereby, Generation Y rank "Price" the second place as a factor affects their travel decision. Generation Z seems to be more cost-conscious than Generation Y and spent less on accommodation on average than Millennials Expedia (2018). To attract and satisfy these young generations, the price strategy should be developed together with value-added experience to be delivered to the customers. As Van Vuuren & Slabbert (2011) suggested, "Don't sell the product, sell the experience". Moreover, "Promotion" can play an important role in encouraging the young generation to make their decision on travelling. This study revealed that Generation Z ranked "Promotion" in second place as a factor affecting their travel decisions.

Additionally, influencer marketing was reported to play an important role in encouraging these two young generations to make purchase decisions. According to Deloitte Global Millennium Survey (2019), online influencers have a significant impact on Generation Z. Around 45% of them are followed by more than 10 online influencers, and more than one in 10 are followed by more than 50. Therefore, influencer marketing should be implemented to encourage an effective type of sales promotion for each generation.

5.4. Place (Channel of distribution) implications

According to this study, the majority of both generations sought information from online resources and social media. This is not a surprise since Generation Y tends to ignore advertising on traditional media platforms such as magazine, radio, and television. Since they grew up during the technology revolution period, they expect the fast, personalised communications on the channels and devices they're accustomed to (Culclasure, 2016). Generation Z will become the largest generation of consumers by the year 2020 and are viewed as digital natives. They are similar to Generation Y, who prefers online booking rather

than traditional booking. They also tend to use online travel agents and third-party websites less. Both young generations are accustomed to social media. The differences may concern which social media forms are popular for each cohort. According to Dickey and Lewis (2010), Generation Y's most popular web sites are as follows: Facebook (100.0%), Twitter (92.0%), Myspace (90.0%), LinkedIn (86.0%), Flickr (75.0%), Xanga (46.0%), and Blogger (39.0%). The Business Insider (2019) reported that Generation Z or social media, members of Gen Z gravitate toward Instagram, Snapchat, and YouTube. Therefore, it is up to the marketers to choose the platform that can most effectively reach each generation.

6. Conclusion

This research is a quantitative examination that aims to identify the differences in travel behaviours and factors affecting travel decisions between Generation Y and Generation Z. The population of this study included Thai people whose ages can be categorised as Generation Y (26- 40 years old) and Generation Z (15- 25 years old). The sample size of the study was 400. Data was collected from the samples using a questionnaire. Data was analysed by a computer program through statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. The research hypotheses were tested by t-test statistics.

The findings of this study revealed that Generation Y and Generation Z Thai tourists share many similar travel behaviours, such as travel objectives, transportation, and season of travel, as well as days of travel, travel destination, and sources of information. However, we also observed some differences in travel behaviours between these two generations, such as travel company, travel decision, influencers, interesting types of tourism, and budgeting.

The study also showed that there was no significant difference in the attitude towards "Product" and "Place" between Thai tourists in Generation Z and Generation Y ($p > 0.05$). Still, differences were observed from the attitude towards "Price" and "Promotion" between the two generations ($p < 0.05$). From the similarities and differences between the two generations, the marketing plan for both generations should be similar in some parts and different in some parts to fit each cohort. With respect to "Product" or tourist destinations, the government and local tourism agencies should develop new tourist destinations and promote them to the two generations as unseen destinations. The "Price" strategy should be developed together with value added experience to make customers feel satisfied. For online marketing and promotion, using online influencers and user reviewers should be implemented as they have a huge impact on these young generations. It is especially essential for marketing targeted at these young generations. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to the efforts of government agencies concerned about the tourism industry in Thailand as well as other countries in Asia.

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